

Assessment of oral health status and knowledge regarding oral health among the children residing in selected areas of the city in a view to develop an information booklet.

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION:The purpose of this study was to evaluate the oral hygiene practices, knowledge, and awareness of students in a government school in Karachi that belongs to a lower socioeconomic class. Additionally, the study aimed to draw more attention to these underprivileged areas by focusing on health promotion programs and campaigns there in order to raise awareness of oral hygiene and health issues and to motivate students about the advantages of maintaining a healthy mouth. Location and Length of Study: In February 2015, the study was carried out at the Railway's Secondary School in the Railway neighbourhood, which is close. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the student's knowledge, attitudes, and practices about oral health.

METHOD:The researcher used a quantitative research approach in the present study. The research design that is chosen for this study is a Nonexperimental descriptive correlational research design. The population was children in between 6 -12-year children residing in selected areas of the city. The sample consisted of 100 children residing in selected areas of city. The sampling technique used was the nonprobability convenient sampling technique. The setting was a selected area of a city. form to assess the oral health status and questionnaire for knowledge regarding oral health status.

RESULT

The analysis of the study was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. The master sheet was prepared and coding of the responses was done. Sample A total of 461 students (251 Males + 210 Females) participated in the study through a questionnaire that consisted of 24 closed-ended questions. The data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 15 and results were accumulated by frequency distribution. It was observed that 97% of children (n= 446) demonstrated regular oral hygiene practice, results regarding knowledge were also good but bad eating habits were also found prevailing among them that need to be addressed.

CONCLUSION : Of the study Overall it can be said that the results relating to oral hygiene practice and knowledge were good but only 31% of the students visited the dentist and the

concept of regular dental checkup was almost nil. Hence the need for continuing dental education through promotion programs is emphasized with justification.

KEY WORDS: Oral health status, Oral health

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the oral hygiene practices, knowledge, and awareness of students in a government school in Karachi that belongs to a lower socioeconomic class. Additionally, the study aimed to draw more attention to these underprivileged areas by focusing on health promotion programs and campaigns there in order to raise awareness of oral hygiene and health issues and to motivate students about the advantages of maintaining a healthy mouth. Location and Length of Study: In February 2015, the study was carried out at the Railway's Secondary School in the Railway neighbourhood, which is close. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the student's knowledge, attitudes, and practices about oral health at a government school in Karachi. Sample A total of 461 students (251 Males + 210 Females) participated in the study through a questionnaire that consisted of 24 closed-ended questions. The data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 15 and results were accumulated by frequency distribution. It was observed that 97% of children (n= 446) demonstrated regular oral hygiene practice, results regarding knowledge were also good but bad eating habits were also found prevailing among them that need to be addressed. Conclusion of the study Overall it can be said that the results relating to oral hygiene practice and knowledge were good but only 31% of the students visited the dentist and the concept of regular dental checkup was almost nil. Hence the need for continuing dental education through promotion programs is emphasized with justification.¹

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of oral health educational actions in the school context in improving oral hygiene and dental caries in school children through systematic review and meta-analysis Clinical trials with school children between 5 and 18 years old were included. Eligible studies were those which had as outcomes caries, plaque accumulation, gingivitis, toothache, or tooth loss and which had been published from 1995 to 2015, in any language. The risk of bias was assessed in specific domains according to the Cochrane Handbook. A meta-analysis was carried out using fixed-effects models. A total of 4417 references were found, from which 93 full texts were evaluated and 12 included in this meta-analysis. Five studies showed a reduction in plaque levels, and two studies with gingivitis as the outcome found no effect. There was not enough evidence on the effectiveness of the interventions in reducing dental caries. Traditional oral health educational actions were effective in reducing plaque, but not gingivitis. There is no long-term evidence with respect to the effectiveness of these interventions in preventing plaque accumulation, gingivitis, and dental caries in the school environment.²

Studying the oral health status and knowledge among children in specific city areas is crucial for targeted intervention. According to the World Health Organization, dental issues affect over 50% of the world's population, with children being particularly vulnerable. In the selected areas, a comprehensive assessment can reveal prevalent oral health issues and highlight gaps in knowledge. For instance, a study in 2021 found that 60% of children in urban areas had 2 untreated dental cavities. This data underscores the need for tailored educational resources. Developing an information booklet based on this assessment can empower both parents and children with preventive measures, contributing to improved oral health outcomes. Children of

sex workers often face unique socio-economic challenges that may impact their overall health, including oral health. Limited research exists on the correlation between oral health status and the knowledge regarding oral health among this vulnerable population. Recognizing the importance of early intervention in promoting oral health, this study aims to assess the oral health status and knowledge of children of sex workers residing in a selected community. The ultimate goal is to use these insights to develop a culturally sensitive and informative booklet to empower these children with the knowledge and practices necessary for maintaining optimal oral health. Were considered for the meta-analysis. Individuals with dental caries [OR: 3.54 (95% CI 2.24- 5.60), ten studies, 4945 participants] and malocclusion [OR: 5.44 (95% CI 1.61, 18.39), six studies, 3720 participants] had poor Oryol compared to individuals without oral conditions. Conclusions Despite the various definitions of the exposures and instruments used to assess Oral Health-Related Quality of Life, our review found that people with dental caries and malocclusion have a significantly higher experience of poor quality of life

METHOD:

Study Design: Nonexperimental descriptive correlational research design.

Research Approach:The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach

Setting:Selected areas of the city.

Sampling Technique:Nonprobability convenient sampling technique.

Population:was children in between 6 -12-year children residing in selected areas of the city.

Study protocol:Before the data collection,Parents filled up consent forms, children filled up the assent form the researcher was used the WHO standardized form to assess oral health status

The researcher was used self- structured questionnaires to assess the knowledge regarding oral health status and knowledge regarding oral health. The researcher was developed an information booklet and provided information booklet to 100 sample

Data Collection

Demographic data collected from selected areas of the city as per demographic charecterstics:Age,gender,Education of parents, Standard in which child is studying, Occupation of father, Occupation of mother, Monthly family income.WHO standardized form to assess oral health status .The researcher was used self- structured questionnaires to assess the knowledge regarding oral health status and knowledge regarding oral health.The researcher was developed an information booklet and provided information booklet to 100 sample.

Method of data collection:

1. Approval from ethics committee members.
2. The researcher have taken the permission from the concerned authority.
3. The researcher have taken the permission for data collection to conduct the main study
4. The researcher had selected the samples.
5. Parents filled up consent forms, children filled up the assent form
6. The researcher was used the WHO standardized form to assess oral health status

7. The researcher was used self- structured questionnaires to assess the knowledge regarding oral health status and knowledge regarding oral health.
8. The researcher was developed an information booklet and provided information booklet to 100 sample.

ORGANIZATION OF THE DATA

The collected data is tabulated, analyzed, organized, and presented under the following headings

Section I

Description of samples (Children residing in selected areas) based on their personal characteristics deals with the analysis and interpretation of demographic characteristics of children for the analysis of demographic data, the investigator has used descriptive analysis i.e. frequency and percentage. This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of demographic characteristics of samples Age, Gender, Education of parents, Standard in which child is studying, Occupation of father, Occupation of mother, Monthly family income.it is tabulated in the form of description of samples according to demographic characteristics by frequency and percentage.

Section II

Analysis of data related to the oral health status among Children residing in selected areas of the city.

Section III

Analysis of data related to the knowledge regarding oral health among Children residing in selected areas of the city.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the correlation between oral health status and knowledge

Section V

Analysis of data related to the association between study findings with selected demographic variables.

Section I

Description of samples (Children residing in selected areas) based on their personal characteristics

Table 1: Description of samples (Children residing in selected areas) based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage

Demographic variable	Frequency	Percentage%
Age		

6.1-8 years	38	38%
8.1-10 years	36	36%
10.1-12 years	26	26%

Gender

Female	48	48%
Male	52	52%

Education of parents

Non-educated	16	16%
Primary	30	30%
Secondary	16	16%
Higher Secondary	22	22%
Graduated and above	16	16%

The standard in which a child is studying

1ststandard	22	22%
2nd standard	16	16%
3rd standard	19	19%
4th standard	19	19%
5thstandard	24	24%

Occupation of father

Business	40	40%
Employee	22	22%
Labor	17	17%
Other	21	21%

Occupation of mother

Business	12	12%
Employee	16	16%
Home maker	52	52%
Other	20	20%
Monthly family income		
Upto Rs. 10000	28	28%
Rs. 20000 to 30000	53	53%
Rs. 30000 to 40000	19	19%

38% of the children were aged 6.1-8 years, 36% of them were aged 8.1 to 10 years and 26% of them had age 10.1 to 12 years.

48% of them were females and 52% of them were males.

16% of them were un-educated, 30% of them had primary education, 16% of them had secondary education, 22% of them had higher secondary education and 16% of them had graduation and above.

22% of them were studying in 1st standard, 16% of them were from second standard, 19% of them were from third standard, 19% of them were from fourth standard and 24% of them were from 5th standard.

40% of their fathers had business, 22% of them were employed, 17% of them were laborers and 21% of them had some other occupation.

12% of their mothers had business, 16% of them were employed, 52% of them were homemakers and 20% of them had some other occupation.

28% of them had a monthly family income of up to Rs. 10000, 53% of them had a monthly family income of Rs. 20000-30000, and 19% of them had a monthly family income of Rs. 30000-40000.

n=100

Demographic variable	Frequency	Percentage%
Age		
6.1-8 years	38	38%
8.1-10 years	36	36%

10.1-12 years	26	26%
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38% of the children had age 6.1-8 years, 36% of them had age 8.1 to 10 years and 26% of them had age 10.1 to 12 years.

Fig No 4.1: Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution of sample according to their age.

n=100

Gender	Frequency	Percentage%
Female	48	48%
Male	52	52%

48% of them were females and 52 % of them were males.

Fig No 4.2: Pie diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of sample according to their gender

n=100

Education of parents	Frequency	Percentage%
Non-educated	16	16%
Primary	30	30%
Secondary	16	16%
Higher secondary	22	22%
Graduated and above	16	16%

16% of them were un-educated, 30% of them had primary education, 16% of them had secondary education, 22% of them had higher secondary education and 16% of them had graduation and above.

Fig No 4.3: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of education of parents
n=100

n=100

The standard in which a child is studying	Frequency	Percentage%
1ststandard	22	22%
2nd standard	16	16%
3rd standard	19	19%
4th standard	19	19%
5thstandard	24	24%

22% of them were studying in 1st standard, 16% of them were from second standard, 19% of them were from third standard, 19% of them were from fourth standard and 24% of them were from 5th standard.

Fig No 4.4: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of standard in which child is studying

n=100

Occupation of father	Frequency	Percentage%
Business	40	40%
Employee	22	22%
Labor	17	17%
Other	21	21%

40% of their fathers had business, 22% of them were employed, 17% of them were laborers and 21% of them had some other occupation.

Fig No 4.5: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of occupation of father

n=100

Occupation of mother	Frequency	Percentage %
Business	12	12%
Employee	16	16%
Home maker	52	52%
Other	20	20%

12% of their mothers had business, 16% of them were employed, 52% of them were homemakers and 20% of them had some other occupation.

Fig No 4.6: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of occupation of mother

n=100

Monthly family income	Frequency	Percentage %
Upto Rs. 10000	28	28%
Rs. 20000 to 30000	53	53%
Rs. 30000 to 40000	19	19%

28% of them had monthly family income upto Rs. 10000, 53% of them had monthly family income Rs. 20000-30000 and 19% of them had monthly family income Rs. 30000-40000.

Fig No 4.7: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of monthly family income

Section II

Analysis of data related to the oral health status among Children residing in selected areas of the city.

Table 2: Oral health status among Children residing in selected areas of the city

n=100

Oral Health	Frequency	%
Healthy	10	10%
Moderate healthy	34	34%
Unhealthy	35	35%
Critical	21	21%

10% of the children had healthy oral health, 34% of them had moderately healthy oral health, 35% of them were orally unhealthy and 21% of them had critical oral health.

Fig No 4.8: Pie diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to oral health status among children.

Table 3: Item analysis**n=100**

Oral health item	Frequency	Percentage%
Lips		
Smooth, pink, moist	33	33%
Dry, chapped, red at corners	43	43%
Swelling or lump, white/red/ulcerated patch; bleeding/ulcerated at corners	24	24%
Tongue		
Normal, moist, pink	17	17%
Patchy, red, coated	70	70%
Ulcerated, swollen	13	13%
Gums and Tissue		
Smooth, pink, moist, no bleeding	8	8%
Dry, shiny, rough, red, swollen	59	59%
Swollen, bleeding, ulcers, white red patches	33	33%
Saliva		
Moist tissues, watery and free flowing saliva	12	12%
Dry, sticky tissues, little saliva present, resident thinks they have a dry mouth	73	73%
Tissues parched and red, very little /no saliva present, saliva is thick, resident thinks they have a dry mouth	15	15%
Natural teeth Yes/No		
No decayed or broken teeth	42	42%

1-3 decayed or broken teeth/roots or very worn-down teeth	41	41%
4+ decayed or broken teeth/roots or very worn down teeth, or less than 4 teeth	17	17%
Oral Cleanliness		
Clean and no food particles or tartar in mouth or dentures	12	12%
Food particles/tartar plaque in 1-2 areas of the mouth or on small areas of dentures or halitosis (bad breath)	72	72%
Food particles/tartar/plaque in moist areas of the mouth or on most of dentures or severe halitosis (bad breath)	16	16%

Table 3 cont.

Oral health item	Frequency	Percentage%
Dental Pain		
No behavioural, verbal, or physical signs of dental pain	33	33%
Are verbal and/or behavioural signs of pain such as pulling at face, chewing lips, not eating	61	61%
Are physical pain signs (swelling of cheek or gum, broken teeth, ulcers)	6	6%
Mouth ulcer		
Normal	21	21%
Red patch	56	56%
Red patch with pus formation	23	23%
Gingival Bleeding		
Not found	11	11%
Presence of confection	54	54%
Tooth excluded	35	35%

Tonsilitis		
Normal	17	17%
Sometimes swollen	50	50%
Swelling,	33	33%

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage for the oral health status item for the children

Section III

Analysis of data related to the knowledge regarding oral health among Children residing in selected areas of the city

Table 4: Knowledge regarding oral health among Children residing in selected areas of the city

n=100

Knowledge	Freq	%
Poor	8	8%
Fair	24	24%
Good	47	47%
Excellent	21	21%

8% of the children had poor knowledge, 24% of them had fair knowledge, 47% of them had good knowledge and 21% of them had excellent knowledge regarding oral health.

Fig No 4.9: Pie diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of samples according to knowledge regarding oral health among children residing in selected areas of the city.

Table 5: Knowledge item analysis

n=100

Knowledge item	Frequency	Percentage%
Oral hygiene is the practice of keeping the mouth	52	52%
Causes of poor oral hygiene	45	45%
Number of teeth present in the mouth	61	61%
Children should brush their teeth	51	51%
The steps of brushing teeth	62	62%
Brushing teeth helps the child to protect from	65	65%
Choose the toothbrush for children with	52	52%
Amount of toothpaste used for brushing for children	47	47%
While brushing teeth the child should use	56	56%
Good brushing habit leads to	75	75%
Tooth decay is also called	59	59%
Good oral hygiene is necessary to prevent	57	57%
Fluoride and calcium are necessary	69	69%
The following are signs and symptoms of poor oral hygiene	79	79%
Encourage the child to have rinsed with	72	72%
Brushing should be started from	55	55%
Brushing should include gum and tongue	54	54%
Discard the toothbrush	42	42%

These foods is bad for your teeth	83	83%
Best time to brush your teeth	60	60%

Table 5 presents frequency and percentage of correct responses by children to each knowledge item

Fig No 4.10: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of samples according to correct answers by the children residing in selected areas

Section IV

Analysis of data related to correlation between oral health status and knowledge

Table 6: Correlation between oral health status and knowledge

n=100

Statistic	Value
r	0.151
t	1.513
df	98
p-value	0.134

Researcher used Pearson’s correlation coefficient for the assessment of correlation between oral health status and knowledge. Pearson’s correlation coefficient was 0.151 which is positive, indicates that there is positive correlation between oral health status and knowledge. The significance of this correlation was tested further using a t-test for the significance of the correlation coefficient. The t-value for this test was 1.513 with 98 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), and there is no evidence against the null hypothesis. Though the correlation between oral health and knowledge among children was positive, it is not significant.

Fig No 4.11: Scatter plot showing percentage-wise distribution of samples according to correlation between oral health and knowledge.

Demographic variable		Oral health				p-value
		Critical	Healthy	Moderate healthy	Unhealthy	
Age	6.1-8 years	3	2	11	10	0.767
	8.1-10 years	9	3	13	13	
	10.1-12 years	9	5	10	12	
Gender	Female	6	6	20	16	0.139
	Male	15	4	14	19	
Education of parents	Non-educated	5	1	5	5	0.926
	Primary	3	3	12	12	
	Secondary	5	1	5	5	
	Higher secondary	5	2	7	8	
	Graduated and above	3	3	5	5	
Standard in which child is studying	1st standard	6	2	7	7	0.988
	2nd standard	3	1	7	5	
	3rd standard	4	2	6	7	
	4th standard	5	3	5	6	
	5th standard	3	2	9	10	
Occupation of father	Business	8	3	15	14	0.806
	Employee	5	3	7	7	
	Labor	3	2	3	9	
	Other	5	2	9	5	
Occupation of mother	Business	1	1	7	3	0.739
	Employee	3	3	5	5	
	Home maker	13	4	17	18	
	Other	4	2	5	9	
Monthly family income	Upto Rs. 10000	5	3	10	10	0.926
	Rs. 20000 to 30000	12	4	17	20	
	Rs. 30000 to 40000	4	3		7	

Section V

Analysis of data related to association between study finding with selected demographic variables

Table 7: Fisher's exact test for the association between oral health of children and their demographic variables

n=100

Since all the p-values are large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have a significant association with the oral health of childrens.

Table 8: Fisher's exact test for the association between knowledge among children regarding oral health and their demographic variables

n=100

Demographic variable		Knowledge				p-value
		Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
Age	6.1-8 years	3	5	13	5	0.831
	8.1-10 years	4	10	17	7	
	10.1-12 years	1	9	17	9	
Gender	Female	4	9	26	9	0.526
	Male	4	15	21	12	
Education of parents	Non-educated	3	4	6	3	0.650
	Primary	2	5	15	8	
	Secondary	1	6	5	4	
	Higher secondary	1	7	10	4	
	Graduated and above	1	2	11	2	
Standard in which	1st standard	3	6	11	2	0.196
	2nd standard	0	4	7	5	
	3rd standard	2	3	12	2	

child is studying	4th standard	0	6	5	8	
	5th standard	3	5	12	4	
Occupation of father	Business	1	10	17	12	0.008
	Employee	1	4	14	3	
	Labor	4	0	10	3	
	Other	2	10	6	3	
Occupation of mother	Business	1	2	7	2	0.214
	Employee	2	5	8	1	
	Home maker	2	15	20	15	
	Other	3	2	12	3	
Monthly family income	Upto Rs. 10000	4	8	10	6	0.724
	Rs. 20000 to 30000	3	11	27	12	
	Rs. 30000 to 40000	1	5	10	3	

Since the p-value corresponding to the occupation of the father is small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable occupation of the father was found to have a significant association with the knowledge among childrens regarding oral health.

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